

Evolve sense of homeland by performing cultural remembrance in Chimbay

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Summary: The information about some cultural architectural heritage objects in the territory of the Republic of Karakalpakstan is given in the article, the significance of the historical architectural places in forming the youth love for the country is shown.

Key words: Cultural heritage, moral heritage, complex, object, house museum, sense of homeland

Valorous of Uzbekistan, national poet of Republic of Karakalpakstan and Uzbekistan, Ibrayim Yusupov is one of the widespread poet. He was born in 1929 on 5th of May in village Azat which is situated in Chimbay. He was keen on literature when he was studying at school. The poet Ibrayim Yusupov left a vestige which is never cleared. The poet graduated Nukus state pedagogical institute and started working as a teacher there. He worked as a head editor of Amudarya in 1961-62, in institute of history, language and literature, named after Nadjim Daukaraev ,as an assistant ,head of department in 1962-65, in 1965-80 he worked as a head editor of newspaper named "Erkin Karakalpakstan" during next years in choir of public protection of piece,as a head of public cultural center. The poet

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Ibrayim Yusupov become a member of writers union. The poet Ibrayim Yusupov was marked as Honored worker of Culture of Uzbekistan, National poet of Uzbekistan and Karakalpakstan laureate of Berdakh and Hamid Olimjon prizes of republic[1].

He was awarded the Order of the Red Banner, the Order of Friendship of Peoples, the Order of Honor of the Nation and the title of Honorary Professor in 1999, and then in 2005 was awarded the title of Hero of Uzbekistan .Poet Ibrayim Yusupov died in 2008 at the age of 79. Shavkat Mirziyoyev said that in order to perpetuate the name of the poet and turn it into a cultural center, the work of poets and writers should be heard by the people and the whole world.In 2014, a statue of

the poet Ibrayim Yusupov was erected in Konshi mahalla of Chimbay district, and the academic lyceum located there was named after him. In addition, a room was allocated in the academic lyceum and a museum was organized. The museum named after Ibrayim Yusupov in the academic lyceum under TashMAU was organized in November 2011 by Ametova Gawhar. Originally there were 45 exhibits here, today there are about 2,000 exhibits[2]. The manuscripts belonging to the poet are the writing instruments he used, the items belonging to him are books, a collection of souvenir newspapers, gifts, clothes and so on. This museum serves as a center of information for today's youth about the life and work of the poet Ibrayim Yusupov. Madiyar Yusupov and Aygul Niyazova built a house museum of the poet in Azat village of Shimbay region, where the poet lived, and another statue of the poet was erected there. Every year on May 5, writers and poets from the Republic mark the birthday of the poet Ibrayim Yusupov in front of the House Museum[3].

In it, the poems of the poet are recited and performed by young people. The abundance of such cultural places serves to educate the younger generation in the

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spirit of love for them, carefully preserving our nationality. The establishment of this museum is an opportunity for today's young people to learn about the poet and increase their knowledge by reading books. The younger generation will have information about their history. His children Madiyar Yusupov and Aygul Niyazova built a house museum of the poet in Azat village of Shimbay region, where the poet lived, and another statue of the poet was erected there. This house museum seems to be telling the younger generation about the poet's childhood life, the poet's work. The house museum of the poet tells the young generation not only about his work, but also about the village where the poet lived. One of our biggest goals is to increase students' love for the Motherland and to make such cultural relics available to the general public by organizing trips to the home museums of such celebrities.

Behind the big city, There is a small village, On the shores of Kegeyli. Visitors from all over Uzbekistan visit the academic lyceum of the hero of Uzbekistan Ibrayim Yusupov in Chimbay district and the house museum in his native village. I invite you and the younger generation to visit the museums of our great ancestor, which is our cultural heritage.

References

1. J. Bazarbaev's "Poet whose wisdom is combined with beauty"
2. Information about the house museum of Jarekeev Iskender aga, the manager of the house museum.
3. Information about the home client at the academic lyceum under TashMAU was received from G.Ametova.

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